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Mini Review

Should National Environmental Policy focus on developing more oil resources or developing renewable energy sources?

Abstract

United Arab Emirates (UAE) is a nation which is gifted with abundant reserves of oil and natural gas, thus occupying seventh position in the world. Because of its vast reserves, the oil sector plays a pivotal role in running the economic system of nation. Though the country has been making steady progress in other industries such as real estate, tourism, aviation etc. the oil industry holds the key role in its sustenance and development. However, at the same time the world is threatened by the rapidly depleting natural resources like coal and petroleum. While on the other hand their demand is on a sharp rise, due to the constantly growing population and their needs. The capital city of UAE, Abu Dhabi too is witnessing a steeply rising population level due to several factors like immigration of expatriates. With the growth in population, the pressure on the available resources is increasing exponentially.

Besides this, the UAE has the largest carbon-foot-print in the world. Thus, it is essential to develop the renewable energy resources simultaneously, which will help to conserve the natural resources apart from supporting the economy and enhancing the energy security of the country. The paper attempts to journey through certain prominent measures taken by UAE in this direction and their respective consequences [1].

Introduction

Owing to its bountiful oil-reserves, the United Arab Emirate (UAE) is one of the world's wealthiest nations, with a GDP per capita estimated at around \$48,158. According to the Oil & Gas Journal 2012 estimates, the United Arab Emirates is the seventh-largest oil-rich nation with proved reserves of crude oil (97.8 billion barrels). UAE alone holds 7 percent of the world's total crude-oil reserves. Majority of reserves (approximately 94 percent) are located in Abu Dhabi. Oil-rich Abu Dhabi is on a strong growth trajectory and its strong economic position is likely to continue in future [2].

In the UAE, energy demand is on an exponential rise due to the population and economic growth. Moreover, the fast depletion of its primary energy generation resource i.e. fossil fuel emphasizes the need to look for alternatives (Figure 1).

UAE has one of the highest carbon foot-print in the world which has become a major issue demanding immediate attention.

Renewable energy will supplement the energy needs of the

nation and reduce its over-dependency on the conventional sources of energy. It will also help to safeguard its energy security concerns.

GCC: Hydrocarbon Dependency 1/

Figure 1: Trends in hydrocarbon exports versus total exports of goods and services in UAE.

Masdar inaugurated the project Shams 1 in March 2013 which has grown up to become one of the world's largest Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plants and the first of its kind in the Middle East & North Africa (MENA) region. Its capacity of this solar thermal project is around 100-megawatt (MW). Masdar has joined hands with Total and Abengoa to realize this mission [1].

By January 2016, Masdar reserved 80% share by purchasing Abengoa's 20% stake in the asset [1].

Masdar clubs the clean energy generated on site through the 10MW solar power plant and along with the 1MW rooftop solar panels installed on the Masdar Institute buildings which is primarily supplying the national grid. The total energy generated totals up to approximately 19,100MWh's of electricity annually, displacing 11,450 tonnes of carbon emissions each year. This much amount of energy is capable enough to fulfil the energy needs of 500 homes in the UAE for an entire year [1]. (Figure 4) The solar installations map for the UAE [4].

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Policy

Country	RE Policy	RE mechanism	RE Target		RE Projects		
			Primary energy	Electricity	Type	Electricity Produced	Installed Capacity
		Quotas			Hydropower	7.50%	27.759 (GW) as of 2009
UAE	Quotas, Bidding and Subsidies			7% by 2020	Solar PV		10 (MW)
					Solar thermal		100 (MW)

Figure 3: Capacity and potential computation of Solar PV, solar thermal and hydropower in UAE.

Figure 4: The solar installations map for the UAE [4].

However, there are no additional legislations or mechanisms to promote power generation. The policy target of 7% share of renewable energy in electricity generation by 2020 set by the UAE (Abu Dhabi) government can be achieved by implementing strategies such as feed-in tariffs, renewable portfolio standards (RPS), capital subsidies or grants, investment tax credits, sales tax or VAT exemptions. In addition other incentives that are of significance include the green certificate trading, direct energy production payments or tax credits, net metering, direct public investment or financing and public competitive bidding.

Conclusion

Oil resources have been the major source of revenue generation in the UAE. It is because of this very fact itself that UAE can be considered amongst the richest nations of the world in terms of its GDP. There are still substantial reserves of oil in the UAE that can be used both by the nation as well as can be exported for years to come.

However, the ever increasing population, rapid consumption of energy resources and the high carbon-foot-print of the nation have become causes of concern in the recent past. While the present quantity and the sustainability of oil reserves in the UAE seem promising, the fact that it's a conventional natural resource makes it crucial to search for ways of conserving it. The best way would be to develop alternate energy sources by utilizing solar and wind energies to generate power. The emphasis has to be on developing the renewable energy sources simultaneously with the further development of the oil sector. The likelihood of further major discoveries of oil reserves in the UAE is low, but enhanced oil recovery (EOR) techniques are being successfully utilized to increase the extraction rates of the UAE's mature oil fields. Along with this, the development and successful implementation of renewable energy resources will stabilize the system and promote its holistic growth.

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